

ISic0176

I.Sicily inscription 0176

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Circumstances of discovery unknown, in the museum at Termini when first recorded

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 24 cm

Width 30 cm

Depth 8 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]ettio Fausto

2. [---]ius Optatus

3. [s]ibi et suis

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285259

EDR 127474

EDCS 22100107

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7405 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 98

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